

Table 2. Estimated effect modification (Case-only OR/RRR) by personal characteristics of suicides and unexpected deaths other than suicide

Personal Characteristics ^a		Suicides				Unexpected deaths other than suicide			
		3-day lag OR / RRR		7-day lag OR / RRR		3-day lag OR / RRR		7-day lag OR / RRR	
		PE	95% CI	PE	95% CI	PE	95% CI	PE	95% CI
Age	less than 40	1.09	(1.03, 1.15) *	1.06	(1.01, 1.12) *	1.05	(0.93, 1.18)	1.04	(0.93, 1.17)
Sex	Male	1.12	(1.07, 1.18) *	1.12	(1.07, 1.18) *	1.02	(0.96, 1.07)	0.97	(0.92, 1.02)
Job	Agriculture	0.99	(0.87, 1.13)	1.09	(0.96, 1.24)	0.89	(0.78, 1.03)	0.98	(0.85, 1.13)
	Company	1.02	(0.92, 1.12)	1.01	(0.92, 1.11)	0.94	(0.83, 1.07)	0.99	(0.87, 1.13)
	Other	1.07	(0.95, 1.19)	1.05	(0.94, 1.17)	0.87	(0.75, 1.00)	0.91	(0.79, 1.06)
	Unemployed	1.12	(1.02, 1.22) *	1.08	(0.98, 1.18)	0.92	(0.82, 1.02)	0.97	(0.87, 1.09)
Marital status	Unmarried	1.04	(0.98, 1.10)	1.06	(1.00, 1.12)	1.04	(0.95, 1.13)	1.04	(0.95, 1.13)
	Widowed	0.83	(0.77, 0.89) *	0.90	(0.84, 0.97) *	1.00	(0.94, 1.06)	1.08	(1.02, 1.15) *
	Separated	1.11	(1.03, 1.19) *	1.16	(1.08, 1.25) *	1.08	(0.98, 1.20)	0.96	(0.86, 1.07)
Area	Urban Area	1.26	(1.17, 1.35) *	1.27	(1.18, 1.37) *	1.00	(0.92, 1.09)	1.05	(0.97, 1.14)

a Respective References are as follows: Age = "Older than age 40", Job = "Self-employed" , Area = "Rural Area", Sex = "Male", Marital status = "Married", * p < 0.05, PE:point estimate, CI: confidence interval